

Research

Comparative study on the changes of the livelihood status of fisherman community on inside and outside embankment of Meghna Dhonagoda irrigation project

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Abstract: A comparative study was conducted on changes of the livelihood status of inside and outside of Meghna Dhonagoda Irrigation project. A total of five villages with 135 households head from inside and 134 from outside the embankment were randomly selected on the study area. Due to construction of embankment, 21% fisherman of inside the embankment changed their main profession of catching fish and working as fish trader (12%), fish farmer (3%), small trader (5%) and service (1%), whereas, on the outside of the embankment only 8% of them changed as fish traders (3%) and small traders (5%). All fisherman of outside the embankment use to fish in river, while, 64% and 36% of inside the embankment fish in rivers and public ponds with 10-15% share as harvesting cost, respectively. Although communication and other facilities have been developed inside the embankment, in case of fisherman it shows no significance at all. Although loan and health facilities of inside fisherman is marginally higher than that of the outside fisherman (83% and 75% of inside and outside fisherman, respectively have got loan facilities from NGO, Bank and Private etc.), 80% of the outside fisherman own gears and crafts, which was much higher than that of the inside fisherman (44%). Moreover, 41% and 13% of inside and outside, respectively do not possess any crafts and gears, and fisherman from both sides appeared as landless i.e. inside (97%) and outside (100%). Therefore, the study reveals that construction of embankment is considerably changing the socio-economic condition of inside fisherman than that of the outside.

Keywords: Fisherman, Livelihood, Embankment.

Introduction

Bangladesh is situated in the sub-tropical region with an area of 1,47,570 sq.km. It lies between 20°24' to 26°38' North latitude and 88°01' to 92°40' East longitudes. Fisheries sector plays an immensely important role on the socio-economic development of Bangladesh from time immemorial. Fisheries sector contributes about 2.09% of the total export earning, 3.69% to GDP, 22.60% to agricultural sector and also provide 11% employment opportunity of the country. Annual fish production was 35,48,000 MT in 2013-14 fiscal years. Fish also contribute about 60% to the nation's animal protein intake (DoF, 2015.) In Bangladesh about 475 species are marine and 260 species are freshwater species. Geographically Bangladesh is a country of natural disaster. Every year a large number of crops are damaged due to the flood and natural disaster. As a result, food deficit arises and economic system weakens. The Government has emphasized on agriculture to achieve economic self-reliance by recovering the frequent food deficiency. Additionally, flood control drainage irrigation projects are established with a view to fulfill this target. In Bangladesh there are some small and large irrigation projects. Meghna Dhonagoda project of flood control drainage and irrigation is one of those.

If one element of environment gets changed it affects or changes the others. The establishment of flood control embankment affects the other elements like land, livelihood of human and other physical environments.

Fisher men are one of the most vulnerable communities in Bangladesh. They are poor by any standard and over the years economic condition of the fishermen had further deteriorated. A livelihood is sustainable when it can cope with and recover from stresses and shocks and maintain or enhance its capabilities and assets both now and in future, while not undermining the natural resource base. Meghna Dhonagoda irrigation project influence the livelihood of fisherman both inside and outside of the embankment. It changes the pattern of livelihood of fisherman near the area of irrigation project. The main objective of the present study is to compare the livelihood of status of fisherman community of inside and outside of Meghna Dhonagoda Irrigation Project (MDIP).

Materials and Methods

The present study had been undertaken and completed according to random sampling of inside and outside of five villages of Meghna Dhonagoda Irrigation Project by considering

135 households of fishermen. To compare the livelihood status of fisherman community, face to face personal interview with structural questionnaire was done. Design of the research work is depicted in Fig.1.

Fig. 1: Design of the research work

Study area

The study was conducted on Meghna Dhonagoda Irrigation Project, Matlab, Chadpur. Five fishing villages from inside and the same villages from outside were selected randomly for this study.

Questionnaire survey

The draft questionnaire was developed keeping in view the specific objective of the study and developed it later by conducting interview on a pilot basis to prepare the final questionnaire.

Primary data sources

The primary data were accumulated through field survey at the village level using a well-developed questionnaire. Data were collected both by physical observation and interview with fishermen at house.

Secondary data

Further relevant information on socio-economic condition of fishermen were collected from books, thesis paper, journal, Govt. and non Govt. organizations like as District Fisheries Office, DoF, Bangladesh.

Data analysis

Collected information obtained from the survey was accumulated, grouped and interpreted according to the objectives as well as parameters. The collected data were then edited, summarized and graphical representations were made by Microsoft excel.

Results:

Age group

Fig. 2 shows the age group of fishermen both inside and outside of the embankment. It represents the highest number fisherman found in the age group of 41-50 both inside and outside. Beside this 20-40 and 51-above age group of fishermen are more or less same. In every case of age group outsiders are higher than insider except in the age of 20-40 where insiders are higher than outsiders.

Fig. 2: Different age group of fishermen

Religion:

Fig. 3 indicate that in case of religion, Hindu families are dominant in fishing as a profession of their ancestries and it's about to outnumber the Muslim families. Result also showed that there is no significant difference regarding religion of the fishermen from inside and outside of the survey area.

Fig. 3: Religion of studied fishermen

Migration

Migration is the movement from one place to another due to the availability of better livelihood of people. Data (Fig. 4) of the study area suggested that more outsider (44%) have migrated than the insider (42%), due to the accessibility of fish and fishing scope.

Fig. 4: Migration of fishermen in study area

Occupation:

It was found that the majority of population of inside and outside of the irrigation project directly involves with fishing, which is about 79% of inside and 92% of outside of the survey area. Besides fishing, there were also a minority of people involved with other occupations associated with fishing such as fish trader, fish farmer, small trader and other services. Figure 5 showed that in case of fish farmer, there was no single household was found outside the irrigation project that lives on fish farming directly.

Fig. 5: Diversity of occupation in studied area

Loan facilities:

It's a very common phenomenon that the living cost of the city dwellers and sub-urban dwellers are comparatively higher than the marginal people of remote area of the city, and it's somehow effect the living cost of the marginal people who are living inside the dam. As a result, they had to take excess load than the outsider to cope up with the expenses. Fig. 6 demonstrates the percentages of people who take loan facilities from different NGO, Bank,

Private or local organizations are significantly higher among the inside households of dam area than the people of outside. It was found that, about 83% of the community inside the survey area is receiving loan facilities, which is marginally higher (75%) than that of the outside area.

Fig. 6: Loan facilities received by the fishermen of inside and outside of Meghna Dhonagoda Irrigation Project

Health facilities:

The fig. 7 shows that the health facilities are obtained from Village Doctor, Homeopath and Kabiraj both inside and outside the households of the meghna dhonagoda irrigation project area. Among the various haeth facilities, health service from Homeopath and Kabiraj are much available for the outsider than the insider due to less treatment cost and for many relogious customs and taboos. Most of the people from both inside (58%) and outside (45%) the area are taking health services from village doctor, where indsider are holding the pick position in the bar of taking health services from village doctor than outsiders. Following that the second largest avialable heal service is kabiraj, where outsiders are much benefited than the inside households. Furthermore, the Homeopath was documented as the least and last health service among the households of the servey after area, where in case of taking heath facilities, inside households are 18% in compare to that of the outsiders (21%).

Fig. 7: Health facilities of fishermen

Harvesting tools:

Fishing gears and craft are very important fish harvesting tools for fishermen and, therefore considered as oxygen of every typical fishermen. In the present study the fig. 8 showed that about 80% of insider households who have both gears and craft which is almost double in percentage than the people of outside 44%. But it was found that some fisherman both from inside and outside who have only a single harvesting tool either its gear or craft. There were 41% of people are from inside and 13% from outside who have none either gears or crafts.

Fig. 8: Availability of fishing gear & craft

Sanitary facilities

Facilitated with sanitary toilet is one of the key factors, which are directly related to public health issues. The current study has revealed us (fig. 9) a very poor sanitation status of fishermen majority of fishermen from both inside and outside the irrigation project were found to be using ‘kacha’ toilet, which was 85% for the insiders and 68% for the outsiders.

Fig. 9: Percentage of sanitary facilities

Education:

Education is the main factor to improve the livelihood status of fisherman. Figure 10 showed very poor educational status of fisherman both inside and outside. It was observed that about 66% and 64% of both sides were illiterate, whereas some were attend primary education of about 28% and 31%. Very few of the studied population tried to complete secondary education, which was about 6% and 5% from both inside and outside.

Fig. 10: Percentage of education

Drinking water

Drinking water is one of the prime health concerning issues influences the health status of fisherman. In fig. 11, it was observed that fisherman of inside and outside use tube well water for drinking purposes. It is highest source to take as drinking water, which was about 71% and 81%. Some of them also take river water as drinking water of about 18% and 19%, whereas few (11%) of inside fisherman take pond water as drinking water.

Fig. 11: Drinking water source of fishermen

Electricity facilities

Electricity facilities show the standard of living. Observing fig. 12 it can be that outsider get higher access to the electricity than the inside of the MDIP. About 30% and 21 of inside and outside the embankment, respectively facilitated with power supply.

Fig. 12: Electricity facility of fishermen

Discussion

It was observed that the highest numbers of the fishermen's age were 41 to 50 (%) and the lowest (%) were within the age group of 20-40. It indicates that the middle age groups are involved in fishing activities. Ali *et al* (2009). found that most of the fish farmers (50%) belong to the age group of 31 to 40 years in Mymensingh district. Bhaumik and Saha (1994) reported that the age structure of fishermen at Sundarbans was ranged from 20 to 70 years, which was comparable with the present findings. The study suggested that the majority of fishermen were Hindus and a few were muslims from both inside and outside of the irrigation project. Migration of living places was also almost equal in percentage, which is 42% and 44% for the inside and outside, respectively, but causes of migration are different.

The outsider fisherman migrated to outside due to the destruction of their houses by river erosion and insider fisherman migrated to inside, near to river due to unavailability of fish and fishing scope in natural fish habitat of inside the embankment. In the study area, there was very few secondary passed fishermen about 6% and 5%, primary passed of about 28% and 31% from the both inside and outside, whereas the rest of them were illiterate of about 66% and 64%. According to S. Hossain *et al.* (2014), there was no Higher Secondary School Certificate (HSC) and Secondary School Certificate (SSC) passed fishermen, whereas 16% and 14% of the community had passed class V and able to sign, respectively. 70% of the population of the studied area (mention the name of the area) were found as illiterate. Moreover, Shahjahan (2001) reported that 63.33% of riverine fishermen were illiterate, whereas 31.67% had up to the primary level, and 5% had only made it to the secondary level of education in the Jamuna River. It might be due to the majority of the parents are illiterate and engage the children in fishing activities. Moreover, fishing was found as the main occupation of about 79% of inside and 92% of outside of the survey area. Due to the construction of embankment, 21% of fisherman of inside changed their main profession and

choose to work as a fish trader (12%), fish farmer (3%), small trader (5%) and service (1%), whereas 8% changed from outside as fish traders (3%) and small traders (5%) only. K.M. Rejwan Kabir *et al.* (2012) reported that 70% of fishermen were engaged in fishing as their main occupation, whereas 20% and 10% were involved with agriculture and in daily labor of sand business, respectively. In this study, Insiders have been reported to get higher loan of 83% from NGO, Bank and private etc. than that of the outsiders of 75%. Quddus *et al.* (2000) found that, only 34% of farmers got bank loan for fish culture, while majority (53%) of the farmers expend from their own sources. In this survey area, health services from Homeopath and Kabiraj are much available for the outsiders than the insiders due to the less tremement cost. Most of the people, from both inside (58%) and outside (45%) are taking health services from village doctor. Rahman (2007) found that 44% of the farmers usually receive health services from village doctors, 29% from upazila health complex and 27% from MBBS doctors. Fishermen of insider get low electricity facilities than outside of the embankment of about 21% and 30%. S Khatun *et al.* (2013) found that 74% had electricity facilities and, whereas 26% had no access to electricity. Hossain (2009) showed that 95% of fishermen had electricity facility and 5% fishermen did not get facilities to use electricity. The present study reveals very poor sanitation system in both inside and outside of the embankment. Most of the fishermen use Kancha toilet, which was about 85% and 68%.

They also used Pucca toilet but percentage was very poor of about 15% and 32% in both inside and outside the irrigation project. Ali *et al.* (2009) in his study found that 62.5% of the farmers had semi-*pucca*, 25% had *kancha* and 12.5% had *pucca* toilet. It was observed that highest sources of water to take as drinking water was tube well of about 71% and 81%. Some of them also take river water as drinking water of about 18% and 19%, few (11%) of inside fishermen take pond water as drinking water. Kabir *et al.* (2012) also found that 100% fisher- men's household used tube-well water for drinking purposes, among them 40% had their own tube- well, 50% used shared tube-well and remaining 10% used neighbors tube-well. Both sides of fisherman are landless i.e. inside (97%) and outside (100%). Akter (2001) also found that pond farmers had average land area of 1.63 ha.

Conclusion

In present study revealed that the livelihood status of fishermen is below the poverty level. The socio-economic condition of the fishermen in the adjacent of the irrigation project was not satisfactory. They are deprived majority of the basic needs; a human requires to lead his

life. They suffer from lack of education, drinking water, income opportunities, sanitation etc. Although the status is vulnerable in both sides, the study revealed that the condition of fishermen were very worse in inside even than that of outside of the embankment.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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